

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Public Expenditure for Research and Development in Agriculture in EU, USA, and Japan

62% increased between 2011 and 2022 for the countries considered.

The Eurostat calculates the value of public spending for research and development in the agricultural sector.

Ranking of European countries for public spending value for research and development in the agricultural sector in 2021. The United States are in the first place for public spending value for research and development in the agricultural sector with a value equal to 2,570.39 million Euro, followed by Japan with an amount of 1,923.07 million euros and Germany with an amount of 1,121.62 million euros. In the middle of the ranking there are Belgium with an amount of 78.685 million euros, followed by Finland with an amount of 69.91 million euros and by the Czech Republic with an amount of 62.69 million euros. They close the Cyprus ranking with an amount of 7.7 million euros, followed by Malta with an amount of 0.98 million euros and Luxembourg with a 0.56 million euros.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of public spending and development in the agricultural field between 2011 and 2022. Luxembourg is in second place for the value of the percentage variation of public spending and development in the agricultural field with an amount of 1,550.00% equal to an amount of 0.53 units, followed by Malta with an amount of 550.33% equal to an amount of 0.83 units, and Slovenia with an amount of 258.71% equal to a amount of 9.84 units. In the middle of the standings there are Estonia with an amount of 90.84 % equal to an amount of 4.83 units, followed by Greece with a value of 82.42 % equal to a value of 23.07 units and by Denmark with an amount of 75.82% equal to a value of 59.99 units. Finland closes the ranking with an amount of -24.06% equal to an amount of -22.15 units, followed by Lithuania with an amount of -27.20% equal to an amount of -3.43 units and from Cyprus with an amount of -27.24% equal to an amount of -2.90 units. On average between 2011 and 2022, the value of public spending in research and development has grown on average of an amount equal to 62.47% or an amount of 123.37 million euros.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Specifically, the following Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Greece, Portugal, Austria, Romania, Belgium, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Estonia, Cyprus, Slovakia, Cyprus, Lithuania, Slovenia, Sweden, Malta, Luxembourg, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Netherlands, Norway, France;
- Cluster 2: United States;
- Cluster 3: Japan, Germany, Spain.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

From the point of view of the Clusters median, it appears that the value of the median of Cluster 2 is equal to an amount of 2,570.39 million euros, followed by Cluster 3 or 1,121.62 million euros, C1 51,0985 million euros.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the Euclidean distance. Specifically, the following complex network structure is identified or:

- Estonia has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.026 units and with Slovenia for an amount of 0.025 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Estonia for an amount of 0.026 units, with Slovenia for an amount of 0.023 units and with Lithuania for an amount of 0.018 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Lithuania for an amount of 0.022 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.023 units and with Estonia for an amount of 0.025;
- Lithuania has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.022 units and with Cyprus for an amount of 0.018 units.

There is a simplified network structure between the following countries or:

- Luxembourg and Malta are connected by a report having a value of 0.0026 units.

Conclusions. The value of research in research and development in the agricultural sector has grown in all the countries considered between 2011 and 2022. However, there are some countries in which the value of shopping in research and development has decreased or Finland, Lithuania, e Cyprus. The growth in research and development in the agricultural sector highlights the scientific interest in the primary sector despite its marginality in terms of gross domestic product. In fact, agriculture produces a marginal part of the GDP even if it obviously remains a strategic sector for the development of the population from a food and healthy point of view. Particularly interesting are the connections between the investment in research and development and the application of new IT technologies that lead to the affirmation of the so -called agriculture 4.0. Agriculture 4.0 uses a set of IT tools and drones for data collection and for fertigation or to identify the optimal mix of substances and water to be administered to cultures. Agriculture 4.0 certainly has a negative impact in terms of employment, as it reduces the role of employment in the agricultural field, however it improves the optimization of resources and makes crops more sustainable and convenient. Especially in a context of reducing the available water resources and in the context of climate change, fertigation offers solutions for the optimization of production inputs and for the quality improvement of the products. Furthermore, using technologies such as the blockchain, it is possible to "note" or mark the various steps that bring agricultural products from production to the consumer by increasing the certainty of the supply chain and increasing food safety. Agriculture, therefore, also producing less than 5% of GDP in all pro-capita income countries remains essential. And investments in research and development are essential to calculate how the agricultural system can resist the climate change, completely modifying the idea of agriculture, so much to create production plants allocated in buildings comfortably located in the city in the proximity with consumers. However, beyond the futuristic promises, which in some cases are productive and corporate realities, the doubt remains that the growth of the temperature worldwide of 2-3 degrees may have a very negative impact on agricultural crops. Research and development in the agricultural sector therefore remain essential also to contrast any famines induced by the climate change.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

